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METICOS

A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and
Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

Deliverable D11.1

Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan and Material

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Abstract:	This report includes the overall project dissemination and communication strategy and planning and a description of the primary promotional material and tools that will be used. It includes a comprehensive set of dissemination elements including: logo, official short description, the project website along with the entire social network that will be used to advertise the activities of the project. Dissemination material will be edited in English and the languages of all partners involved.
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Executive Summary

This document provides an overview of the dissemination and campaign strategy of the METICOS project, including information about the identification and implementation of the communication approach (the various dissemination channels, tools and materials used for dissemination purposes) as well as a preliminary approach over the exploitation of the project results.

The project adopts a dynamic dissemination plan from the very beginning of the project in order to:

- Raise awareness about the METICOS project and approach, the benefits and opportunities for target stakeholders,
- Increase engagement and encourage the involvement of targeted stakeholders in the project activities,
- Communicate the project results and ensure the exploitation of METICOS outputs after the completion of the project.

This report was developed for outlining the overall project dissemination strategy. This plan will be reviewed and updated on a regular basis for assessing new dissemination opportunities that are likely to emerge during the project lifespan.

The provided communication and dissemination plan covers branding, the project website, social media channels, electronic newsletters and press releases and such. The monitoring of dissemination activities provides information for the overall targets of the dissemination plan.

1. Introduction

The current document aims to present the dissemination and communication strategy that METICOS will employ to achieve promotion, impact and facilitation of exploitation and sustainability prospects. In order to define the adequate methods to disseminate and communicate METICOS, this plan focuses on the primary dissemination and communication objectives, the key messages to deliver, and the target audiences of the project outcomes.

In this context, the present report:

- describes the dissemination approach,
- elaborates on the goals of the plan and the key messages established and disseminated during project,
- explains the tools and channels that will be used,
- identifies stakeholders that constitute the project target audience,
- sets the ground to ensure the project's sustainability after its completion.

The dissemination and communication plan is intended to be a “live” plan, meaning that it will be regularly assessed and updated based on the forthcoming project's achievements and contributions from partners. It establishes the individual partner responsibilities and timelines, guidelines and suggestions for dissemination and communication under the continuous monitoring of the “WP11: Raising awareness and exploitation roadmap – METICOS standardisation activities” leader.

1.1 Intended audience

This document consists of the plan of dissemination activities that will take place during the project lifespan. This document aims to be a practical tool for the project's dissemination manager and all project partners to efficiently develop their individual and collective dissemination and communication activities and contribute to the project's overall objectives.

In addition, the document can be used as a guide – practical tool for “Horizon2020” – “Horizon Europe” dissemination managers of on-going – future projects, who will be willing to explore METICOS strategy and capitalize on it, as well as a dissemination guide/control point for the reviewers of the European Commission.

Ending, the current deliverable report can be used by any possible future replicator of the METICOS dissemination approach.

1.2 Document structure

The document is organized as follows:

The document is structured into the following 7 sections: Chapter 1 “Introduction” introduces the document's intended audience and its structure. Chapter 2 “Dissemination and Communication Strategy” describes target groups, communication messages, channels and tools and planning and evaluation. Chapter 3 provides information on the “Dissemination tools” that will be used during this period. Chapter 4 consists of an of the Social Media Strategy and relevant accounts, while Chapter 5 provides an introduction to the exploitation activities and is followed by Chapter 6 “Monitoring and Evaluation. Finally, Chapter 7 consists of the conclusions of this deliverable report. Two Annexes containing templates for reports and templates for presentations are also available.

2. Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Dissemination of METICOS aims to raise awareness of the project among the target audiences of specific stakeholder groups that constitute the project's community, thus maximising the outreach of the project activities and results. The goal is to ensure that adequate information and key messages are shared with the appropriate audiences on a timely basis utilizing the most effective channels and methods.

Since all project partners are involved in the dissemination and communication efforts, the emphasis is given on managing and engaging the Consortium to participate in the dissemination activities fostering awareness, transferring key messages and achieving impact, especially in their own countries and abroad.

According to the Grant Agreement, **Dissemination** and **Communication** activities are referred to different articles. Even though both terms may overlap and fuel each other, they still feature some distinctive characteristics:

Article 29 states that *dissemination consists of disclosing a project's results to third parties by appropriate means, while the protection of data and inner-project confidentiality are respected. Using scientific publications and other similar mediums project partners have to circulate knowledge among stakeholders that can make use of such knowledge, thus enabling the value of project's results to be potentially wider than the original focus. Hence, the dissemination procedures seek to share material mainly with organisations relevant to the project, such as **research institutes, policy makers, NGOs, corporations, associations, etc.** who can exploit the results of the project. Because dissemination aims at the same direction as exploitation, the content is more specific and scientific. Dissemination includes various **reports created during the project, conference presentations, workshops, newsletters to Stakeholders, synergies with EU-related projects and more.***

Article 38.1 states that *communication has to promote both project's actions and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in strategic and effective methods. Partners have to deploy a communication campaign throughout a project's duration, in order to make the research activities known publicly **in a way that such actions can be understood by non-specialist audience.** Also, the communication activities must address the public policy perspective of EU research and innovation funding, by considering aspects such as the transnational cooperation in a European consortium (i.e. how working together has allowed to achieve more than otherwise possible), or the scientific excellence and the contribution to solving societal challenges. Communication includes **media publications about METICOS's aspects, press releases and newsletters, social media promotion, offline and tangible material like posters and brochures.***

Bearing in mind the above, METICOS's dissemination and communication strategy incorporates both actions into its planning and aims at answering the following key questions:

- **Why** disseminate and communicate?
- **What** to disseminate and communicate?
- **When** to disseminate and communicate?
- To **Whom** to disseminate and communicate?
- **How** to disseminate and communicate?

The following sub-chapters elaborate on the enlisted questions to provide a detailed overview of METICOS's dissemination and communication plan.

2.1 Why Disseminate and Communicate

This part is set to provide context regarding why METICOS needs to be disseminated and communicated. The rationale for a carefully designed dissemination and communication plan is based on the requirements for **attaining the maximum possible impact for the project** by reaching a variety of audiences and communicating the right message to the right audience. METICOS elaborates a multifaceted plan with overlapping activities that will engage different target groups, because this is essential for the project's development steps in terms of awareness promotion, feedback and collaboration attainment, and cultivation of sustainability and exploitation prospects.

As a result, the objectives of the dissemination strategy are formed to jointly satisfy specific needs. The goals of the present planning can be identified as below:

- **Engagement of stakeholders:** to achieve its ends, METICOS has to seek to engage with a body of third parties that will act as potential contributors to the development, evaluation, uptake, and exploitation of its outcomes and encourage their participation in the project's actions on a systematic and regular basis. Raising public awareness of project achievements among the key user groups and stakeholders in the IT infrastructure and cyber-security era, the scientific community, and the general public is the main focus.
- **Awareness building:** to secure a certain level of impact and promote METICOS as a sustainable tool. It is crucial for METICOS to work towards the cultivation of its awareness status in the diverse environments of the target audiences.
- **Feedback extraction:** as METICOS is a brand new and innovative project, it is expected to produce a series of reports and tools. It is purposeful to disseminate such materials towards niche audiences that will grasp such knowledge and provide valuable critical insights about it. As one of the results, METICOS will facilitate the sharing of knowledge inside the Consortium and establish the project communication & dissemination methodology, which could also be used by the members of the Consortium or any other third party as a good practice.
- **Collaboration fostering:** as METICOS is operating at a cross-European and multidisciplinary level, there are multiple entities that would be of great influence on the project in terms of creating a network of organisations that operate on the same level and domain. The latter, along with the upcoming project activities, will lead to the development of a business plan for the project tangible outcomes, including cost-benefit & cost-effectiveness analysis for all exploitable project foreground. Moreover, it is expected that the project will proceed to the identification of challenges and gaps in the ongoing business data security standardization process and provision of targeted mandates for improving current related standards.

The above aspects comprise the main objectives of METICOS's dissemination strategy and dictate the methodology and the targeting of the dissemination and communication actions.

2.2 What to Disseminate and Communicate

This section refers to the key outcomes that should be disseminated and communicated during the various phases of the project. In order to meet the aforementioned goals, the dissemination and communication plan should set the goal of what messages should be promoted.

The following **key METICOS outcomes/messages** have been identified for dissemination and communication:

- **METICOS Pilot Activities**
- **METICOS Platform**
- **Process-oriented Knowledge**
- **Sustainability and Exploitation activities**
- **METICOS Network of data sources application**
- **Established and good practises around EU countries**
- **Policy Recommendations**
- **METICOS will conduct an analysis to secure positive societal impact and maximize border control process efficiency.**

2.3 To Whom to Disseminate and Communicate

In order to be effective, the project’s dissemination and communication strategy will be selective about the choice of audience and will be strategic about its approach to that audience. A scattergun approach (using all possible avenues throughout the project's life) may hit the suitable desk at the right time. Still, a targeted and strategic approach is likely to be more fruitful.

METICOS will involve various stakeholders from different organisational, economic and social contexts. Below we have regrouped them into specific categories. It needs to be noted that this is a live list. Thus it will be updated during the project lifespan so that we can achieve the maximum possible reach.

Border Control Sector	End users	Facilitators
Technology Providers, Scientific community, Civil Society Organizations, Defense Industry	Border Authorities, Facility managers, System operators, Commercial Customers, Stakeholders at the Pilot Sites, General Public	EU Institutions (EC, European Science Foundation, MEPs), National public authorities (industrial committees, national regulation authorities, Ministry and regional councils), Standardisation Bodies, Related EU-funded projects, Organizations & EU Alliances in topics addressed by METICOS European Technology Platforms and respective clusters Public Bodies & Environmental Organizations, General Public

Table 1 METICOS Identified Stakeholders

2.4 When to Disseminate and Communicate

In order to ensure that the timing of activities is appropriate, we identify three dissemination and communication stages:

- **Early in the project**, dissemination and communication aim to ensure that the project addresses the needs of the different target groups, creating awareness and understanding of its activities both within the Consortium and among peer groups. In addition, a dialogue mechanism with the target groups through interviews and social media will be initiated, enabling them to provide constant feedback during the whole course of the project.
- **During the project**, dissemination and communication are about identifying lessons, particularly in receiving feedback from target groups and stakeholders, and adjusting the

project's strategy and developed components in order to maximize effectiveness and efficiency. At this stage, it is also important to inform the research community about the research results of the project and ensure appropriate peer review. Project research results will be published in high-quality journals and presented in workshops, seminars, and conferences. Online activities (expected Webinars) will ensure broad participation of the target audience (SMEs, entrepreneurs, end-users, and such) in the project's activities.

- **At the end of the project**, dissemination and communication will publicize more generally the project's outputs, the lessons learned, and the benefits gained. Such dissemination and communication will also aim to build up a constituency of support for the project's follow-up activities. Dissemination activities will focus on providing evidence to support the long-term sustainability of the METICOS platform and the rest exploitable solutions.

For the proper execution and implementation of the project activities, a series of control points have been identified, accompanied by a series of monitoring tools.

The first series of control points have been identified from the beginning of the project, actually from the proposal stage. Those are the project Deliverables and the Project Milestones. Although different meanings and purposes are correlated with each of the two, there are indeed ways that do secure (in general) a first identification of the available time and of tasks that do need to be performed.

2.4.1 WP Deliverables & Time

D11.1	Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and Material	6
D11.2	Dissemination, communication and exploitation progress report	18
D11.3	Dissemination, communication and exploitation final progress report	36
D11.4	Regulatory and standardisation report	36

Table 2 WP 11 Deliverables and Timetable

2.4.2 WP11 Milestones

Num.	Milestone title	Due	Means of verification
MS8	Analysis of current standards, regulations and Market Issues	9	Analysis of current standards, regulations and Market issues completed
MS9	First Commercialisation Plan	12	First Release of Market Analysis and User Segmentation.

MS10	Analysis of available Business Models	12	Analysis of Business Models completed
MS11	METICOS Ecosystem overall evaluation and new business model validation	36	Detailed report for the outcomes of METICOS completed and new Business Models available
MS12	Public Awareness & Dissemination	36	Detailed report on the dissemination outcomes
MS13	Final Exploitation Strategy & Stakeholder Engagement	36	Detailed report on the exploitation strategy completed & stakeholder engagement available

Table 3 WP11 Milestones and Timetable

2.4.3 METICOS Online KPIs Monitoring Tool

In addition, to these control points that accompany the project implementation process, the project consortium has agreed on a more detailed timetable regarding the implementation of the communication and dissemination activities. An online – live monitoring document has been developed in order to keep a real-time track of the KPIs of WP11, with projections on the expected results divided per project semester as well as online dissemination planning greed with alerts on the frequency of posts, publications, and shares that are expected to take place, securing the proper engagement. The “Project’s Overall Target” column contains the KPIs and targets as those are stated in the project Grant Agreement (initial or amended). The “currently achieved” column includes the current total of all semesters, while for each semester, there are the “Expected” and “Achieved” columns, respectively. The table is being updated frequently and according to the project status, period, and needs. It needs to be noted that the expected KPIs for each semester are being calculated via a mathematical formula and by dividing the total to 6 minus the previously achieved total. Thus, there might be cases-semester where the “achieved” is lower than the “expected”, but this is purely due to the way the “expected” is calculated. By taking into account the rest semesters, we can have a much clearer picture. Ending, for the KPIs that are not foreseen in the Grant Agreement or for the ones that are due to the end of the project, there are still some “semesters expected goals” but these are also correlated with project internal and external factors and the project implementation phase. As it is clearly presented in the following table, incorporated in the current document in August 2021, and also described in detail in the current document’s relevant sections, the project has overachieved the expected and self-defined KPIs.

		Projects Overall Target	Currently Achieved	Expected M1-6	Achieved M1-6	Expected M7-12	Achieved M7-12	M1 Sep	M2 Oct	M3 Nov	M4 Dec	M5 Jan	M6 Feb	M7 Mar	M8 Apr	M9 May	M10 Jun	M11 Jul	M12 Aug	M13 Sep	M14 Oct	M15 Nov	M16 Dec	M17 Jan	M18 Feb
Dissemination Report																									
General Dissemination Metrics																									
Website traffic																									
	Page views	5000	4886	833	1491	833	3395	0	0	0	286	303	902	887	528	817	806	357							
	Downloads	200	47		6		41						6	13	9	12	7								
Social media Followers:																									
	Facebook		388	0	96	0	292		10	15	23	48	51	80	75	13	73								
	Twitter		155	0	38	0	117		3	26	9	33	14	38	16	16									
	LinkedIn		135	0	28	0	107		3	4	11	10	12	3	30	34	8								
	Total Social Media	5000	678		162	1000	516		16	19	60	67	96	97	163	63	97								
	Facebook Posts Reach		4607	-	-	-	4607																		4607
	Facebook Post engagement		303	-	-	-	303																		303
	Facebook Post impressions		5043	-	-	-	5043																		5043
	Twitter Impressions		20375	-	-	-	20375																		20375
	Twitter Profile Visits		4342	-	-	-	4342																		4342
	Twitter Mentions		30	-	-	-	30																		30
Press releases and																									
	Nr of Newsletters		6	2	1	1	1	1																	
	Nr of Press releases		10	0		0	2	0																	
Scientific publications																									
	Number of papers		9	0	2	0	2	5 to be																	
	Number of conference			2		2	0	0		1	1														
	Number of workshop			4		0	4	0								2	2								
	Number of networking events		13	10	-	-	-	10								9	1								
	Cluster projects		8	9	1	0	2	9																	
	Number of blog entries		50	22	8	4	8	18	1	1		1	1	9	1	3	2	3							
	Number of Videos	by end of project - 3	0	-	-	-	0	0																	
	Video Views			0	0	0	0	0																	
	Brochures		500	0	83	0	83	0																	
Project Specific Metrics																									
	Organisation of a training	3/30 delegates	0	-	-	-	-	-																	
	Feedback sessions	3/ 40-70 per event	0	-	-	-	-	-																	
	Participation in external	>30	6	-	2	-	4		1	1					2	2									
	Final Conference	500	0	-	-	-	-	-																	

Table 4 METICOS WP11 KPIs Online Tracker

		M1 Sep	M2 Oct	M3 Nov	M4 Dec	M5 Jan	M6 Feb	M7 Mar	M8 Apr	M9 May	M10 Jun	M11 Jul	M12 Aug	M13 Sep	M14 Oct	M15 Nov	M16 Dec	M17 Jan	M18 Feb
WP11																			
Visual identity	Domain		X																
	Logo			X															
	Partner's logos, Partners description and contact info to be added at Website			X															
	PowerPoint presentation				X														
Promotional materials	Document templates				X														
	flyers, postcards and brochures will be created, printed and electronic format							X											
Website	Promotional videos							X											
	Basic website design, site map, wireframe								X										
Social media accounts	Developed web-design (presented to the consortium for commenting as well)																		
	First version of the website online (15th March)																		
Other dissemination products	Creating social media accounts (FB page, Twitter, LinkedIn)			X															
	Official press releases newsletter every six months (containing 8 news items)							X											
Events conferences	Create an Event Tracking Template/ attend/ future attending/ interesting events (Contribution- All partners)								X										
Materials to support																			

Table 5 METICOS WP11 KPIs and activities Planner

2.5 How to Disseminate

The dissemination and communication plan is based on two levels of strategies for the dissemination of the project's intermediate/final as well as partial / global results and of its progress:

- The **Consortium's overall strategy**, that is the dissemination and communication strategy in which the Consortium plans and acts as a whole.
- The **individual strategy of each consortium member**, according to the specific type of organisation, infrastructure, role and resources in the project, etc.

The dissemination and communication strategy includes activities that can be divided into internal and external dissemination and communication according to the target audiences they are addressed to.

The **internal** dissemination and communication include the instruments and activities that intend to give awareness of the results destined for the consortium members and the Advisory Board and that are not available to the public in general. This kind of dissemination includes:

- Project meetings and their resulting reports (physical, virtual)
- Information exchange, e.g., through mailing lists
- A collaborative workspace document repository
- Video and phone conferencing
- Reports, publications, deliverables, etc.
- On-line collaboration through different means, e.g., dissemination report form submission, regular WP and Task-related meetings, online documents collaboration, blog posts and comments from partners, doodle polls, etc.

External dissemination and communication are referred to activities and means which create awareness of the project's partial and overall results and document the project's progress. The target of those dissemination activities is specific users and interest groups that have been identified above as well as the end-users.

METICOS proposes a hybrid approach for the effective dissemination of its aims and results, facilitated by a variety of activities, both external and internal and is based on:

- achieving reputation or a "name in the field" by using the media (including social media), speaking at conferences and writing for journals;
- networking – making and sustaining personal contacts
- capturing the interest of existing initiatives (e.g. European Day for Border Guards (www.ed4bg.eu), FRONTEX Conference and Exhibition on Biometrics on the Move (frontex.europa.eu), International Summit on Borders (www.internationalsummitonborders.com), IEEE Intelligent Systems (formerly IEEE Expert)", the "IEEE International Conference on Automatic Face & Gesture Recognition (FG 20xx)", the "IEEE International Conference On Biometrics: Theory, Applications And Systems", the "BEST Network Conference at BIOSIG", the "FRONTEX Conference on Biometric Technology for Border Control", the "International Conference on Ethics and Policy of Biometrics and International Data Sharing", and the "International Conference on Security Science and Technology (ICSST)", Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI), International Conference of the BIOSIG Special Interest Group (BIOSIG), Perceptual Quality of Systems (PQS).

- visiting decision-making units and attending to EC and National workshops and info days; communicating with other project consortiums;
- and being contactable, accessible and creative.

The general dissemination and communication activities that will be carried out in the project are listed in the table below.

Activities		Main Means
Dissemination and Communication	Internal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Project Meetings (physical, virtual) ▪ Project Reports ▪ Publications, Deliverables (common templates) ▪ Internal Newsletter ▪ Online tool
	External	
	Online dissemination and communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Project Website, Project Newsletter ▪ Social media channels (Twitter / Facebook / LinkedIn / Research Gate / SlideShare channel)
	Distribution of Promotion Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Logo ▪ Publications in scientific/specialised magazines ▪ Press Releases ▪ Brochures, Posters ▪ Reports
	Organisation/ Participation of/ in Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Participation and presentation of the METICOS project in conferences, workshops, exhibitions, symposia, etc.
Establishing Contacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Personal Contacts with Key People ▪ Participation in Workshops/ Conferences ▪ Project Meetings (formal & informal) ▪ Targeting of scientific community, authorities, Policy Makers ▪ Continuation activities 	

Table 6 List of METICOS dissemination and communication activities

3. Dissemination Tools

To effectively promote the aforementioned messages and address how they will reach the target audiences, the strategy must embed them into proper formats. That is, METICOS has to select what kind of tools and channels are going to be utilised to realise the dissemination and communication actions. Various online and offline means, direct and indirect, are necessary to make the project activities and results available to the target groups. Such methods are manifold, including online options (website, emails, social media), mass media and networks (media presence, social networks, partners' networks, etc.), or offline tangible actions, like events, posters, brochures, etc. Depending on the project audiences, an adequate set of methods is going to be jointly employed.

Below, there is a detailed description of the tools and channels that METICOS will utilise during its lifecycle.

3.1 Project's Visual Identity

The project's visual identity comprises several features and elements that are necessary for the project promotion and representation, including visual and textual key points:

METICOS logo: The project logo plays an important role in creating the project identity. It is included in all documents, dissemination materials, presentations in events and conferences, and online channels.

Figure 1: METICOS project logo

In any communication material, deliverable, presentation, etc., produced in the frame of the METICOS project, apart from the project logo, the flag of the European Union will be illustrated.

Figure 2: EU flag

The EU flag will always be accompanied by the following statement: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 883075"

METICOS document templates: aligned with the logo's role, a specified set of format characteristics is fundamental. A great volume of deliverables, reports, and presentations produced by project partners

is going to be disseminated, so a defined template is prepared, in order to ensure professional diligence and compliance with EU’s guidelines to all the project’s documents, presentations, and communications.

METICOS posters and flyers: The METICOS posters will be developed in English for all countries and in local languages whenever needed. Hard copies will be made available in order to distribute them to events, which partners prepare or participate in. Posters will be updated when new information is available.

All information and content developed for the communication and dissemination uses of the METICOS Project will be available on the Project website under a dedicated tab titled “Media Kit” and can be accessed [here!](#)

3.2 Community Research and Development Information Service

The Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS) is the European Commission’s primary source of results from the projects funded by the EU’s framework programmes for research and innovation (FP1 to Horizon 2020). [CORDIS](#) has a rich and structured public repository with all project information held by the European Commission, such as project factsheets, participants, reports, deliverables and links to open-access publications.

Figure 3 METICOS Project Information on CORDIS

METICOS, as all projects funded by the European Commission, holds its own ‘Factsheet’ within CORDIS. Accessible [here!](#) Besides the simple project description, METICOS has communicated with CORDIS HelpDesk and has updated the project factsheet sub-page, including also ways to connect with the project. A third user can now use this factsheet to visit METICOS project website and social media accounts, while one can access the latest tweets of the project without even leaving the site.

Figure 4 METICOS latest tweets via CORDIS

3.3 METICOS Website

The project’s website operates as the major source of the project’s identity, goals, and actions, from which every stakeholder category can be informed. In other words, METICOS website is a central dissemination and communication tool of the project providing the main results of the METICOS research and outcomes. In particular, the METICOS website aims at:

- Providing information about the project, its main objective, description of the produced outputs and knowledge, publications, latest news and upcoming events in which METICOS will participate, information about project partners and related projects introduction with a link to their websites, subscription to project’s newsletter, social networks and contact info.
- Presenting information to stakeholders so that they will understand the reasons to get involved and how they can participate in the project’s activities.

The Home Page of the METICOS website is presented below:

Figure 5: Home page of the METICOS website

METICOS Website Dendrogram

METICOS Website consists of five (5) main menus and 12 sub-menu tabs containing information per tab topic. The information is allocated under each tab and sub-tab in order to provide the user/visitor/reader with the best possible experience and guide them in order to find out as much as possible about the METICOS Project.

➤ The Project	○ About
	○ Consortium
➤ The Platform	○ Pilots
➤ Publications	○ Public Deliverables
	○ Scientific Articles
	○ Presentations
➤ Synergies	○ Related Projects
➤ Communications	○ News
	○ Events
	○ Newsletter
	○ Media Kit

Figure 6 METICOS Website Menu structure

METICOS Website Sitemap

• https://meticos-project.eu/
• https://meticos-project.eu/about/
• https://meticos-project.eu/consortium/
• https://meticos-project.eu/advisory-board/
• https://meticos-project.eu/platform/
• https://meticos-project.eu/pilots/
• https://meticos-project.eu/publications/
• https://meticos-project.eu/deliverables/
• https://meticos-project.eu/scientific-articles/
• https://meticos-project.eu/presentations/
• https://meticos-project.eu/synergies/
• https://meticos-project.eu/related-projects/
• https://meticos-project.eu/stakeholders-community/
• https://meticos-project.eu/communications/
• https://meticos-project.eu/news/
• https://meticos-project.eu/events/
• https://meticos-project.eu/newsletter/
• https://meticos-project.eu/media-kit/

Website Performance

For the whole duration of the project, and in order to evaluate the performance in terms of reaching stakeholders and acting as a source of information, we use standard web traffic analysis tools to track the number of visitors and other similar metrics.

To do so, we will use the available Google Analytics, and we will track a series of factors, either individually either in correlation with each other.

A list of the factors to be taken into account, accompanied by a short explanation, is available below:

- **Users:** An individual person browsing the website (technically, a unique browser cookie)
- **New users:** People that visit the website for the first time in the selected date range.
- **Sessions:** A single visit to your website, consisting of one or more page views, along with events, e-commerce transactions and other interactions
- **Page views:** A pageview is reported when a page has been viewed by a user on the website
- **Avg. Session duration:** Provides a top-level view of how long users are spending on the website. Google Analytics does not count time for the last page viewed during a session. This means that average session duration will tend to be skewed lower than the actual amount of time people are spending on the website.
- **Bounce rate:** Bounce rate is the percentage of sessions with a single page view. Bounce rate provides us with great insights about the performance of the content.
- A **session** is the period time a user is actively engaged with your website, app, etc. All usage data (Screen Views, Events, E-commerce, etc.) is associated with a session.
- **Users** have initiated at least one session during the date range
- **Pages/Session** (Average Page Depth) is the average number of pages viewed during a session. Repeated views of a single page are counted
- **% New Sessions** is an estimate of the percentage of first-time visits.

In terms of specific tailored security measures:

The **security issue** is the first that was taken into account when we were building this website. Brute force attacks, hacks on retrieving usernames, hacks on logins, etc., are blocked. Plus, there is a software firewall running behind the website to prevent “suspicious” IPs from accessing the website. The identification of the “suspicious” IPs is being made automatically; “suspicious” actions are also being logged. Vulnerabilities that exist on other websites have been extinguished. The security section is being updated constantly.

Ending, the website is SEO friendly, and after a period of time, google results will bring the website to higher ranks. This does not only depend on the website itself, back-links must also be included from other websites, e.g., partner websites, links on social media, etc. This procedure is a 2-way procedure. Moreover, we have implemented Libraries so keywords will be easily searchable by Google.

The website will be maintained throughout the project cycle and will remain active for at least 3 years after the official completion of the METICOS Project.

All public information on the METICOS website is available with no restrictions and can be accessed by any visitor with no need to create an account or give any personal data. This information and all webpage-related data are backed on a regular basis.

3.4 Media Content

In order to effectively disseminate and communicate METICOS towards the diverse set of stakeholders, the project's strategy has to leverage the promotion possibilities of mass media channels by formulating media materials that will be disseminated through the following channels:

Newsletters: Inform multiple target stakeholders about the project progress, news, and upcoming events and activities and raise further awareness. This option is suitable for dissemination and communication purposes, due to its direct and periodic fashion. Also, media organisations can receive METICOS's newsletters, which will enable the project to be mediated to stakeholders via credible platforms of high prominence.

The circulation of METICOS newsletters will take place approximately every six months through mailing lists and contact databases accumulated by project partners, in full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation. The content of such media is going to consist of information pieces about the project's key completed actions, events where METICOS has been presented, international conferences and/or exhibitions, and news about relevant projects and planned activities and events. All versions of the newsletters will be prepared in English and distributed digitally.

Building the Newsletter: METICOS newsletters are not just emails forwarded to a simple mailing list. Marketing platforms such as MailChimp will be used in order to create engaging and attractive content (a mix of text, images, videos, links, and such others), providing users with clear, easy to navigate and easy to share sophisticated and friendly content. This is also proven by the engagement data provided by those marketing platforms, an additional feature that provides the project with the opportunity to track the engagement and to adjust the content accordingly in order to maximize the reach and recipients' engagement

Moreover, via the use of those marketing platforms, recipients have the opportunity to find more about the project, the project's communication accounts, and project activities besides those mentioned as the main part of the newsletter, since they can find all the relevant links and channels, reports and material available in all newsletters via dedicated tabs and buttons, which are part of the main newsletter template for all the campaigns.

Currently, the number of subscribers is more than **111**. Taking into account that our first E-newsletter campaign is now under development, we consider such a number as a great start for our E-Newsletter campaigns. We must also note that the content of each newsletter is expected to be communicated to additional (third) users via its' publication on the project's website, via partners actions – sharing the newsletter to their established communities, via synergies sharing, and last but not least via project's social media accounts.

The subscription option is available at the bottom of the METICOS website. No pop-up windows or advertising windows are added, respecting this way the user and the user experience. When one

selects to subscribe, one is transferred to a new dedicated (and provided by MailChimp) window, where users can safely provide their contact information (simply their email addresses. Name and Surname are not obligatory). The procedure ends with a humanity process confirmation.

Figure 7 Mailchimp Subscription pages

Moreover, following the guidelines provided by Mailchimp regarding subscribers' engagement, most of the campaigns will be re-sent the day after the official issue to the non-openers. This tactic actually replicates the original campaign and sends it to a segment of unresponsive subscribers, maximising the initial reach and engagement by at least 9%.

The first METICOS E-Newsletter was developed and disseminated on February 2021, following the 6-months timeline that's was decided for the communication and dissemination of project e-newsletters. The 1st E-Newsletter is available as all project e-newsletter will be on the project website under the menu tab "Communications" and the corresponding sub-tab "[Newsletters](#)".

GDPR Compliance: In addition, via the use of those tools, the METICOS will be in full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation, which was implemented on the 25th of May 2018. Subscribers, have the right to opt-out from the newsletter mailing list, find out why they are receiving the newsletter while their information (email address) is stored in a dedicated mailing list under the protection and the terms and conditions of the [MailChimp platform](#), with which the subscribers have agreed during their subscription to the METICOS mailing list, when they have subscribed.

Press Releases: in addition to newsletters, press releases provide a more formal manner that is channelled towards national or European media organisations. METICOS will prepare press releases so as to raise awareness and disseminate information about the project. Press releases will refer to pivotal project events or relevant milestones. Such media material will be published on the project website,

on METICOS's social media platforms and through press contacts of the partner organisations; translation of the content to more languages than English will be conducted where necessary.

News Entries: the periodic circulation of the above media content has to be complemented with a frequent and specific form of publication about METICOS's progression. Thus, the project will elaborate on sharing news on the project website as a dissemination and communication method that will provide updates in a sustainable frequency about the actions of Consortium members. In their majority, blog entries will refer to either METICOS's presence in networking events or METICOS's progress of work.

3.5 Publications

Publications are a significant element for METICOS dissemination strategy; they constitute a dissemination tool that informs and engages the METICOS community about and with the projects' procedures, methodologies and outcomes. The projected body of reports conducted by project partners, is not only going to fuel METICOS's development but will also facilitate its dissemination planning. This category is consisted of two overlapping elements:

Deliverable Reports: a considerable volume of partners' work efforts are focused on conducting research and producing reports. This material is valuable in terms of effective dissemination of the project's contribution. The public deliverable reports will be uploaded on an open access repository supported by European Commission, Zenodo¹, and the dedicated Community establish exclusively for the METICOS Project – [Zenodo METICOS Community](#).

“All information and material related to the public, such as public deliverables, brochure, posters and so on, will be freely available on the project website. When IPR of foreground knowledge needs to be protected, the corresponding disclosures will be published.”

“All deliverables include a set of keywords and a brief description that aim to facilitate the indexing and search of the deliverables in search engines. The keywords in each deliverable aim to stress the main topics addressed in the documents.”

“The audience of the public deliverables of METICOS range from general audiences, interested in activities performed in the project, to more specialised audiences in the different sectors and stakeholders or those who wish to learn about the benefits of METICOS through the experiences gathered through the pilots.”²

Scientific Publications: drawing from the above report material, project partners will be devoted to the creation of scientific articles published in the international scientific literature, when possible. All

¹ <https://zenodo.org>

² D2.2 – Data Management Plan, 2.3 METICOS Public Deliverables, p.10, 15.02.2021

Data Analytics methods to measure Quality of Experience and User Acceptance: A review	M12 (August, 2021)
Development of a decision-support system for technology acceptance in smart border control technologies	M13 (September, 2021)
Agent-based modelling and simulations: A comprehensive review	M15 (November, 2021)
Publication: METICOS TAM approach + Pilot Survey Results	M18 (February, 2022)
Publication: Main Online Survey Results (incl. Cross-cultural & Diversity aspects)	M22 (June, 2022)

3.6 Participation in (E-) Events

An important part of the methods of METICOS’s dissemination and communication is sourced on the real-life, interactive actions that will engage target audiences of METICOS with the project. In conjunction with the above tools and channels, METICOS is going to be promoted to the community of its Stakeholders in ways consisted of the following types of events.

Conferences, workshops, and other events organised by 3rd parties: a plethora of activities regarding the developments on migration, border control, and relative topics are taking place around the world. Such events offer a significant opportunity for METICOS to be disseminated in environments where key stakeholders are gathered. Hence, it is valuable for METICOS’s development and possible impact to participate in events organised by international agencies, fora, and institutions that present expertise around the domain that METICOS covers. Apart from conferences and workshops, which constitute the main types of events by third parties, project partners can also take part in varying events, like networking events, symposia and/or even webinars.

This part of dissemination and communication strategy depends on the good practices between project partners in terms of inner-project communication. That is, partners can share information they receive about upcoming events that present a subject closeness to METICOS’s activities, thus updating the Consortium about new dissemination and networking possibilities. Communicating such information can result in partners assisting other partners and collaboratively boost METICOS’s impact on the projected areas of stakeholders.

The following table shows the planned Communication/dissemination activities and a series of dissemination opportunities (participation in events/ submissions to scientific conferences that METICOS is taking into account.

	European Day for Border Guards (www.ed4bg.eu), FRONTEX Conference and Exhibition on Biometrics on the Move (frontex.europa.eu), International Summit on Borders (www.internationalsummitonborders.com), IEEE
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<p><u>Conferences:</u></p>	<p>Intelligent Systems (formerly IEEE Expert)”, the “IEEE International Conference on Automatic Face & Gesture Recognition (FG 20xx)”, the “IEEE International Conference On Biometrics: Theory, Applications And Systems”, the “BEST Network Conference at BIOSIG”, the “FRONTEX Conference on Biometric Technology for Border Control”, the “International Conference on Ethics and Policy of Biometrics and International Data Sharing”, and the “International Conference on Security Science and Technology (ICSST)”, Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI), International Conference of the BIOSIG Special Interest Group (BIOSIG), Perceptual Quality of Systems (PQS).</p>
<p><u>Journals:</u></p>	<p>Big Data Research, Elsevier. Computational Statistics and Data Analysis, Elsevier, International Journal of Data Science and Analytics, Springer, IEEE Transactions on Big Data, IEEE Big Data, Trans. on Information Forensics and Security, Trans. on Security & Privacy, IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing, Vehicular Technology, Telecommunications and Wireless Communications, Elsevier Computers and Security Journal, International Journal of Migration and Border Security, International Journal of Biometrics, IEEE Transactions on Communications, IEEE Transactions on Multimedia, IET Biometrics Journal, Quality and User Experience Journal, International Journal of Human-Computer Studies, Behaviour and Information Technology, Management Information Systems Quarterly, International Journal of Migration & Border Studies.</p>

Since the beginning of the project, METICOS Project has been presented at the following third-party events:

1. METICOS was presented at the Nicosia Risk Forum “Preparing for the Next Pandemic – the important role of Civil Protection: A Regional View”, that was organised on the 26th of November 2020, by the Project Coordinator. Nicosia Risk Forum is an innovative event for the area of South-Eastern Europe, which brings together **academic, industrial, governmental, policy, and other societal stakeholders with a significant interest in societal safety**. Nicosia Risk Forum was organized under the auspices of HE the Minister of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Cyprus Dr. Nikos Christodoulides. Understandably, due to Co-Vid19 restrictions, #NRF2020 took place virtually. Additional information is available [here!](#)

Figure 9 METICOS PPT presentation at the NRF 2020

- METICOS** was also presented online on Saturday, 5/12/2020, at the [3rd International Conference On E-Business, Information Management, and Computer Science \(EBIMCS 2020\)](#) that was organised in Hong Kong. The 2020 3rd International Conference on E-Business, Information Management and Computer Science was organized by IDSAI, co-organized by IETI, IRIEM, European University Cyprus, Center for Financial and Monetary Research “Victor Slăvescu” of Romanian Academy and Algebra University College, supported by Sustainable Real Estate Research Center of Hong Kong Shue Yan University and JRFM. It aimed at providing an innovative exchange platform for students, faculty, and researchers from all over the world. The conference focused on the frontier topics in the theoretical and applied E-Business, Information Management, Computer Science.

Figure 10 3rd International Conference On E-Business, Information Management, and Computer Science (EBIMCS 2020)

3. Second Secure Societies “Project to policy kick-off Seminar” - 22 & 23 March 2021.

Figure 11 METICOS participation in P2PKOS

METICOS Project virtually attended the Second Secure Societies “Project to policy kick-off seminar” (P2PKOS) organised by the EC and DG Research and Innovation that took place on Monday 22 and Tuesday 23 March 2021. It included participation from 43 projects of the 2019 H2020 Secure Societies call, as well as representatives from the REA, DG HOME (Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs), DG CNECT (Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology), additional EC policy officers and other European agency representatives. On day 1, a half-day session was organised to address communication, dissemination and exploitation issues that are specific to the programme. On day 2, the full day was dedicated to discussions between policy officers from the Commission and project representatives. The project coordinator has presented the project, its aims and objectives, as well as the upcoming steps.

4. European Migration Network (EMN) Event – 24th March 2021

The European Migration Network (EMN) is an EU network of migration and asylum experts who work together to provide objective, comparable policy-relevant information, and knowledge on emerging issues relating to asylum and migration in Europe. We are very pleased to inform you that METICOS, together with PERSONA gave a joint presentation of the Member States' National Contact Points of the European Migration Network (EMN). Additional info about EMN can be found [here!](#)

5. METICOS participating in a closed workshop organised by FRONTEX

Figure 12 METICOS Participation in EBCG workshop

METICOS participated in a closed workshop organised by FRONTEX and the European Border and Coast Guard (EBCG) community (FRONTEX agency and Member States Authorities) on the 20th and 21st of May 2021. The Project Coordinator of METICOS, Pantelis Velanas, PHD, presented METICOS to the European Boarder and Coast Guard community going through the scope and focus of the project and plans for the future. The aim of the workshop was for the European Boarder and Coast Guard community to be familiarised with the H2020 project that are ongoing and identify innovation insertion and operation testing opportunities. More information about Frontex can be found at: <https://frontex.europa.eu/>

6. 1st EFFECTOR Workshop – 21st May 2021

Figure 13 METICOS Participation in 1st EFFECTOR Workshop

The EFFECTOR event was held virtually on 26th May 2021 at 10:00 CET. As the project progresses into its second half, this online workshop gathered end-users, academy and industry to present the project and discuss the results achieved so far regarding the EFFECTOR Interoperability Framework for Maritime Situational Awareness.

During the project lifetime, we will identify more (e-) conferences that will be reported on the METICOS website.

3.7 Synergies with Other Projects and Initiatives

The establishment of synergies with other related EU-Funded projects, relevant initiatives and the European Border Ecosystem in general was envisaged even from the proposal stage of the METICOS Project. This is why there is a dedicated task, according to which *“METICOS will seek out collaboration and synergies with other projects and organizations in order to further enhance existing endeavors and jointly shape the future vision of the field. The METICOS partners will promote interactions with similar projects (FP7, H2020 and beyond) and with other stakeholders like government organisations or departments (e.g. of Interior or Public Safety) and policymakers, research and academic institutions and will exchange non-confidential information with them in order to avoid useless replication of work. Consortium members will also participate in respective “concentration” meetings and dissemination activities, when and if requested by the European Commission.”*

METICOS took the initiative to create the H2020 BES Cluster with the goal to establish an active community of projects that will work together, organise joint events, support each projects’ pilot activities, share information, discuss methodologies that each project prepares, share good practises and services, knowledge, identify common problems as well as solutions to these problems, and exchange ideas about future policy suggestions. Although each project is represented by the Project Coordinator or the Dissemination leader, information and updates on each project’s activities as well as information on the progress of the Cluster are also shared among the different consortia.

The Cluster activities were initiated in January 2021. METICOS has initiated the discussions with the dissemination managers and representatives from the current, but not only, projects, communicating the idea of establishing a joint space, a community where projects with relevant activities could support each other in many different ways, starting with communication, dissemination and exploitation activities to real joint pilot implementation activities, knowledge and practices exchange and use of practices and methodologies.

After informing via e-mails the current members of the cluster about the cluster idea, they latter have agreed to participate in as well as to have an introductory teleconference in the upcoming future. Joint participation in activities organized by European Migration Network, Frontex – the European Border and Coast Guard Agency as well as the European Commission can also be identified as factors that facilitated and expedited the development of such a synergy.

METICOS developed a sub-page under the METICOS official website, where users can find information about the Cluster as well as for each of its’ members, and ways to connect (websites, social media accounts, newsletter subscription links and such). The sub-page is available [here!](#)

In addition, ViLabs – METICOS Communication and Dissemination leader developed an internal mailing list, populated by representatives of each project, that will be used to share information, events, opportunities, news, updates, questions and anything else that the members find appropriate.

3.7.1 Cluster Members

The table below provides information on the members of the Cluster until the period of August 2021 – the date of resubmission of the current document report. It has to be noted that on the original report that was submitted on February 2021, METICOS has established synergy with TRESSPASS Project

and was under discussions with MIRROR, ITFLOWS and PERCEPTIONS. Currently, the members of the Cluster are 10, including METICOS in that list.

	<p>A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology.</p> <p>The EU-funded METICOS project aims to create an up-to-date acceptance classification scheme as well as a societal and ethical impact dashboard of border control technologies, to empower three major sub-divisions of the wider border control sector: travellers, border control authorities and service providers. METICOS will mainly focus on established models and theories, such as the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) and Innovation Diffusion Theory. In addition, performance and credibility expectations of smart border technologies from travellers, border management and law enforcement agencies will be explored in detail. As such, METICOS aims to create a holistic solution to address challenges for border management, both as regards societal acceptance and efficiency. Duration: 36 Months</p> <p>https://meticos-project.eu</p>
	<p>TRESSPASS is a European research project in the H2020 framework and Border and External Security thematic area, receiving EU funding under GA 787120. The overall scope of TRESSPASS is to modernize the way the security checks at border crossing points (BCPs) are held out at land, air and sea. TRESSPASS imports the concept of “risk-based” security checks and proposes an analytic framework for modelling risk as well as a systematic approach of quantifying risk, based on a set of indicators ranging from real-time behaviour analytics to intelligent information extraction and sharing that can accurately be measured across all four tiers of the EU Integrated Border Management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) measures undertaken in, or jointly with third countries or service providers; (2) cooperation with neighbouring countries; (3) border control and counter-smuggling measures, and (4) control measures within the area of free movement. <p>http://www.tresspass.eu/</p>

	<p>MIRROR aims to develop an integrated platform, a set of tools, as well as a systematic methodology for the comprehensive inter-media analysis of the perception of Europe, the detection of discrepancies between perception of and reality in Europe, and the creation of awareness for the impact of such misconceptions.</p> <p>The multidisciplinary consortium consists of fourteen partners from seven countries from research and industry, as well as practitioners. The consortium will cooperate to gain a better understanding of how Europe is perceived abroad and the mechanisms involved in the process. The MIRROR Project was launched in June 2019 and has a time period of three years.</p> <p>https://h2020mirror.eu/</p>
	<p>ITFLOWS will generate novel insights on migration. The purpose of ITFLOWS is to provide accurate predictions and adequate management solutions of migration flows in the European Union in the phases of reception, relocation, settlement and integration of migration, according to a wide range of human factors and using multiple sources of information. These insights will be provided by an evidence-based ICT enabled solution (the EUMigraTool) and precise models. All solutions will have fitness for purpose continually validated by policy-makers and practitioners in cooperation with civil-society organisations in a dynamic and iterative process. ITFLOWS will propose tailor-made solutions for practitioners and policy makers for managing migration. On the one hand, the EUMigraTool targets first-line-practitioners, second-level reception organisations and municipalities. It will provide modular solutions based on the prediction of migration flows and the identification of risks of tensions between migrants and EU citizens. On the other hand, an in-depth analysis on drivers, patterns and choices of migration as well as public sentiment towards migration will lead to the drafting of adequate recommendations and good practices for policy makers, governments and EU institutions.</p> <p>https://www.itflows.eu/</p>
	<p>PERCEPTIONS examines how Europe and the EU are seen by people who have immigrated there or intend to do so. It examines what perceptions of Europe exist among this group, how they are formed, whether they correspond to reality and how they influence migration decisions. PERCEPTIONS also examines how the flow of information could be distorted and whether inaccurate information could lead to a threat to the security of migrants (e.g. through dangerous border crossings) or even national security (e.g. radicalisation).</p>

	<p>https://project.perceptions.eu/</p>
	<p>Funded by the European Commission, PERSONA project has been brought into being in order to come up with a unified and tailored Impact Assessment Method for No-Gate Crossing Point Solutions capable of appropriately evaluating border controlling technologies and of ensuring that these solutions meet the requirements and expectations of governments, LEAS, and border crossing individuals.</p> <p>http://persona-project.eu/</p>
	<p>EFFECTOR aims to enhance maritime surveillance, improve decisions support, and foster collaboration of maritime stakeholders by implementing an Interoperability Framework and associated Data Fusion and Analytics services for Maritime Surveillance and Border Security that will allow faster detection of new events, better informed decision making, achievement of a joint understanding and undertaking of a situation across borders, allowing seamless cooperation between operating authorities and on-site intervention forces ensuring that all existing privacy and data protection rules are fully respected. Specifically, EFFECTOR will unlock the full capabilities of maritime surveillance systems and data sharing at tactical and strategic level by introducing applied solutions for enhanced border and external security, including the implementation of a multilayered data lake platform for end-to-end interoperability and data exploitation, the exchange of enhanced situational awareness pictures at different level with CISE and EUROSUR, the adoption of interoperability standards for exploiting data sources and systems currently underutilized in maritime environment and the demonstration of new concepts and tools for knowledge extraction, semantic representation, data fusion, analytics, and federated querying that can scale from local to regional and up to national and transnational level.</p> <p>https://www.effector-project.eu/</p>
	<p>The overall D4FLY concept is to identify, reduce and avoid vulnerabilities in the identity lifecycle of modern border management, thereby strengthening European Smart Borders against serious and organized crime. It does this by exploring, developing and validating new technologies for identity and document verification – including biometrics-on-the-fly, and even explores how this could work in risk-based border management concepts.</p>

	<p>The D4FLY project will augment the current capabilities and capacities of border authorities in countering emerging threats in document and identity verification (e.g., forged documents, impostor fraud, morphed faces) at manual and highly automated border control points and in the issuance process of genuine documents.</p> <p>https://d4fly.eu/</p>
	<p>Nineteen (19) organizations from twelve (12) European countries joined forces for a new project on technologies which enhance border and external security. The project will combine for the first time a multi-role lighter-than-air (LTA) unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) with an ultra-high resolution multi-sensor surveillance payload supporting border surveillance, search & rescue applications and specifically rough terrain detection.</p> <p>https://borderuas.eu/</p>
	<p>image Manipulation Attack Resolving Solutions</p> <p>The verification of travel documents’ authenticity is key to border checks and forensic investigations. However, the growing complexity of document security and border control pressures often make it impossible to confirm whether documents are genuine or counterfeited. The EU-funded iMARS project aims to provide image morphing and manipulation attack detection solutions for the evaluation of ID document authenticity, ID document verification and fraud detection. iMARS will deliver mobile tools to check document integrity. The technology will be assessed from an ethical, legal and societal perspective, and validated in real border control conditions. iMARS will support standardisation of these solutions and of their evaluation protocols, and will provide training, guidelines and best practices to border guards, document investigators and passport application officers.</p> <p>https://imars-project.eu/</p>

In addition to the activities described above, METICOS Partners will exploit the best way possible the networks and collaborations established before the initiation of project activities, relevant to previous projects that were members of, in order to support the project activities in terms of dissemination and sustainability as well as in actual implementation terms. A series of such projects are noted below:

Relevant projects	METICOS
MITIGATE: Multidimensional, integrated, risk assessment framework and dynamic, collaborative risk management tools for critical information infrastructures.	METICOS will make use of MITIGATE results, in particular the Open Intelligence and Big Data Analytics component, which will be enhanced so as to include advanced premium and exclusive services that are not offered today elsewhere (e.g., root-cause analysis on social media events).
EXPOSe: EXacerbation Prediction Engine: early warning and decision making tool.	Knowledge gained during the execution of EXPOSe project in automated decision/alert tool will be re-used, as well as the collaboration and integration of a real-time processing engine.
COncORDE: Development of Coordination Mechanisms During Different Kinds of Emergencies.	METICOS will benefit from integration expertise for services dedicated to emergency services.
SII ANALYTICS: Integration and operational and analytics recovery to large amounts of data Information system, personnel training and LAN and SAN interconnection networks.	The expertise in Big Data Analytics and Cybersecurity will be brought to METICOS project.
SMILE: SMart mobilLity at the European land borders.	METICOS will benefit of the expertise gained during SMILE implementation, related to specific integration of border management. Expertise also gained in “Front-End modules, interactive GUIs and secure/trustworthy private communications” are directly related to the need for web-based graphical user environment of METICOS platform.

Table 7 METICOS Partners' relevant projects

3.7.2 The #H2020 BES Cluster - METICOS and Plans for the establishment of an active Synergy/Community:

3.7.2.1 Methodology

Cluster Member Selection

H2020 BES Cluster seeks out collaboration and synergies with other projects and organizations in order to further enhance existing endeavours and jointly shape the future vision of the field. The current members of the H2020 BES Cluster are H2020 funded projects that are funded either under the same call, or have related goals and activities (comprising the “future of border control” according to FRONTEX) or due to the importance and expertise of the members of the consortia leading to the second phase of enlargement which will include “other” stakeholders such as government organisations or departments (e.g. of Interior or Public Safety) and policy makers, research and academic institutions.

In particular, for every project, we studied the official description stored at CORDIS Platform website and the project website itself, focusing on the goal, the pilot studies, and the expected impact. After that, we grouped the projects according to the common synergy topic they could have with the METICOS project.

3.7.2.2 *Define method of work*

In order to engage with relevant projects in common synergy activities, we started by **inviting** them with an official letter giving special emphasis on the motivation and the expected common impact. All contact details are publicly available on the project websites. Some METICOS partners have direct contacts with some of the projects, and that eased the initial communication.

Afterwards, we organised the **means of collaboration**. We requested the project official logo, the website address and social media URLs, so as to publish them on the dedicated webpage, developed by the METICOS project for this synergy. After gathering all the replies, a teleconference was organised to meet each other and establish a first internal connection. After that, a **joint mailing list** has been developed to facilitate our internal communication to share relevant files and exchange information, best practices, and such.

Afterwards, we presented the **plan of activities** and proposed the concrete steps to follow, the means that will be used for the implementation of such activities as well as we set milestones to achieve.

All the information about the METICOS synergies are available on the project website as ‘*Synergies à H2020 BES Cluster*’ which includes the list of projects (logo, title), upcoming events and activities, and informational material and such.

3.7.2.3 *Collaboration topic(s)*

The aim of these synergies is double. First, we would like to exchange useful information between relevant EU projects in order to exchange best practices and methodologies. Secondly, we aim to establish synergies with other projects so as to **exchange ideas about future policy suggestions**. The sustainability/exploitation impact of the project is also highly essential and it is better, if we collaborate with other EU projects to find and propose effective measures for evidence-based policy suggestions.

3.7.2.4 *Activity planning*

In order to collaborate effectively, METICOS will invite the projects and organize a webinar in order to agree on some concrete steps to follow. Turning to the next steps, METICOS would like to: a) communicate in a wider audience the synergy meeting report (that is going to be developed after the first Synergy Online Meeting) in order to increase awareness about it and therefore, receive message of interest to join from other relevant projects, b) communicate the synergy report with other relevant projects, which invited to this meeting and they didn't manage to join, c) enhance the common dissemination and communication efforts by promoting the news on social media.

3.8 METICOS Ethics Board

Due to the severity of the ethics issues raised by the proposed research, an Ethics Board has been established, which includes relevant independent expertise to monitor the ethics issues in this project and how they are handled. The ethics advisory Board consists of internationally known scientists in relevant fields.

3.9 METICOS Security Advisory Board

The Security Advisory Board contributes to the definition of the data management plan and the monitoring of METICOS security challenges. SAB is chaired by the Project Security Officer (PSO) Mr. Mohamed Abomhara, Researcher at the Department of Information Security and Communication Technology of NTNU and includes a representative from all the partners qualified in security management and handling of document classification. It is in charge of the security and classification issues and the approval of the candidates of the Use Cases Group. All deliverables produced by the consortium or material for dissemination will undergo security scrutiny organised by the PSO in collaboration with the SAB, who will decide the classification level and to whom the data can be disseminated.

Moreover, SAB members will have to review the deliverables, publications, and other dissemination material, ensuring that no sensitive information will be disclosed.

The SAB consists of one member from each LEA participating in the project, with representatives from different security disciplines from the involved LEAs. It constitutes a well-informed – expert body that is going to provide with feedback and insights to the project and the project research implementation and knowledge development, while it will constitute a bridge with third Law Enforcement Agencies. Due to the nature of the board and of its members affiliations, no additional information can be shared within this public deliverable report.

4. Social Media Strategy & Accounts

4.1 Social Media Strategy

Social media channels are an integral part of our dissemination and communication strategy as they provide the chance to get connected and reach regions and stakeholders all over the world. The aim of this section is to present the basic elements of the social media strategy and the channels that will be used for the project. Our overall approach is based on the figure below, which represents our specific strategy using social media as a modern tool, which is constantly updated and aligned to changes and new features, to help us promote the project and its activities and explore new possibilities for reaching the relevant audience. The general approach is easy and quite simple, and it is described in the figure below. The figure shows the path the project will follow in order to identify the stakeholders, the relevant channels and increase the impact. There are 3 steps: Boot up, set up and manage up.

4.2 METICOS Social Media Accounts

Social media platforms are a much-needed part of METICOS dissemination and communication strategy, as they allow engaging the interested audience and representing the project activities via an interactive and direct platform of communication. Through the use of social media, METICOS can manage a steady flow of information towards diverse audiences during its development and communicate the outcomes of partners' work continuously. This way, METICOS can sustain a well-informed group of target audiences, which will enhance the project's overall impact.

The METICOS dissemination and communication team has chosen to utilise social media accounts on Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Research Gate. Using content that matches each platform's structural affordances and features SEO characteristics (e.g., relevant hashtags) combined with the partners'

already existing accounts, METICOS accounts are going to be used to increase project visibility in social networking sites.

The elaboration of social media as means to dissemination and communication of METICOS is based on a specific approach. The opted strategy reckons that social media constitute a modern tool, which is constantly updated with new options and features. Hence, such platforms can promote the project and its activities by adapting its communication messages to any given new feature offering new possibilities for reaching relevant audiences.

In the planning stages of the METICOS project, it was decided to build social media presence to represent the consortium members, the Pilots and the project in an integrated way. Its main goals are to bring attention to the project website, amplify its content, support communication and encourage participation in the pilots activities. Four social media channels will be used: Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and YouTube.

The following table was developed as initial thoughts before setting up the accounts, and it was discussed as a basis with the Consortium.

Channel	Rationale	Frequency
Facebook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The most popular network. Most of the partners maintain Facebook pages that can provide us with our first audience. Many features to capitalize on including video posting, events, photos, carousels, promoting the open calls in different ways without a limitation in characters. There is the option to use advertisements to promote the page and the application. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Post twice a week. More if the available content is critical.
Twitter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A popular network with short and concise messages. Easy to use. Many projects & relevant stakeholders use it. Project partners have accounts with many followers and dedicated audience. Based on past experience, Twitter is a successful tool for projects; Helps to live blogging during events. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Almost on a daily basis, depending on the content. Two tweets per week, if there is no occasion.
LinkedIn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Add useful content, e.g., articles, e-newsletters, etc. Tag organisations so they are able to share the news with their professional network. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> When an occasion to motivate the business, network presents itself. At least one post per two weeks
YouTube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Useful to share the project videos. No wide dissemination of the channel per se, but of the individual videos. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> After interviews or radio/TV broadcasts.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In cases of webinars/teleconferences. • When a video is available.
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Table 8 METICOS Communication Channels

The URLs of METICOS’s social media accounts can be found below:

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/meticos.eu/>
- Twitter: <https://twitter.com/MeticosEU>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/meticos-eu/>
- Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/meticos_eu_project/

In order to achieve and over-achieve the project KPIs, a tracking–monitoring tool is being used as it has already been introduced under section 2.4.3 of this Deliverable report. Although it is not expected or set up as a clear set of targets or KPIs, a detailed record of the project's social media insights is being held. These metrics provide a much better view and understanding of the use and effectiveness of the project social media accounts and could be used to verify the actual reach to users and the communities. These insights provide a much better understanding of the social media usage, the actual- real people that have interacted with the provided content, along with their type of reaction. Moreover, via the users' engagement, post likes, post share, mention and such, a much wider audience that it is not being considered via the simple “page like” is being activated and engaged.

Thus, by tracking and considering this information, the project can track properly and efficiently the actual – real involvement of social media users and adjust the project activities as needed. The engagement rate, used to track how actively involved with the content the audience is and how effective the brand campaigns are. Engaged users interact with brands through interactions such as “likes,” comments and social sharing. This “engagement” does indicate the audience health, how responsive these followers are and how many are “real” followers! The latter is a factor that has to be taken into account where evaluating the strategy, activities and insights of the project social media accounts.

At the granular level, one will look at different engagement metrics:

Likes, Comments, Retweets, etc.: Individual engagement metrics like a Share or a Retweet add up. In a Twitter report, one will see a total number of engagements per post or profile.

Post engagement rate: The number of engagements divided by impressions or reach. A high rate means the people who see the post find it interesting.

Account mentions: Organic mentions, like @mentions that aren’t part of a reply, or tagging without prompting, indicate good brand awareness.

Reach: The number of people who saw any of the posts at least once. Reach is different from impressions, which may include multiple views of the posts by the same people.

Impressions: The number of times the post was on screen.

4.2.1 Facebook

METICOS already has a [Facebook Page](#), which currently (Month of Report delivery) counts presently more than 388 follows. The project logo is used as a profile image, while a dedicated image created exclusively for the METICOS project is used as the cover section of the Facebook Page.

Figure 14 METICOS Facebook account

4.2.2 Twitter

Project-related news and relevant articles from other sources relevant to the METICOS project field of activities are/will be shared for the whole project duration. The target groups will be citizens of the pilot locations, the general public, businesses, NGOs, technological developers and Policy Officials.

The Twitter account, which currently has 155 followers, will be mainly used to promote participatory activities, awareness-raising events, exploitation activities and the project progress in general. It is a great tool to connect with most of our relevant stakeholders. A screenshot below presents the Twitter profile with the logo on the profile image and a tailored cover page, which makes the profile friendlier and warmer for the users, creating positive feelings about it. Users have access to a short description of the project as well as to the link leading to the project website.

Figure 15 METICOS Twitter account

4.2.3 LinkedIn

METICOS LinkedIn account has a dual purpose. It is mainly used to promote professional content and to promote the project activities, but it is also used to motivate users/individuals to reach the members of the Consortium and find representatives of the project in their countries, as almost all the members of the Consortium have connected to the public page with their profiles. METICOS currently has more than 160 LinkedIn connections.

LinkedIn is a professional network and one of the best solutions to build relationships with professionals, migration experts, ICT workers, and other initiatives relevant to the projects' main subject, therefore with key stakeholders. Since it is a professional network; it is crucial to post more sophisticated messages and useful information in a formal way. Posts will be infographics, newsletters, short articles to inform, possible publications, promotion of events, discussions.

Figure 16 METICOS LinkedIn account

Main objectives

- To disseminate the projects objectives
- Raise awareness about the project goals
- Raise awareness about METICOS Activities in the ICT sector
- Engage with professional stakeholders
- Exchange ideas
- Engage in interesting conversations about No Gate Solutions
- Promote project events
- Disseminate newsletters and press releases
- Connect with relevant projects, initiatives, organizations
- Initiate a participatory approach

5. Exploitation Strategy & METICOS Business Models

Within this task, in close liaison with all technical WPs as well as a careful worldwide market analysis that will take place, METICOS aims at evaluating that the exploitation potential of METICOS technologies remains the highest.

Project relevant activities are initiated with the **design of the exploitation strategy**, which will be carried out using the following methodology:

1. A thorough analysis of exploitable foreground per partner and definition of Intellectual Property Rights (licensing approaches, transfer of knowledge to spin-off companies, patents, etc.). Herein, the management of the existing background and the exploitable foreground brought by each partner will take place, following the necessary interaction among partners for having a coherent list of exploitable outcomes.
2. For each exploitable foreground, identification of target stakeholders (relevant product vendors, end-users, etc.) and implementation of dissemination strategy in order to ensure that all relevant target groups are informed about the appropriate activities & outcomes of the project.
3. Identification of tangible financial plans (i.e. through venture capitals, creation of spin-off, H2020 funding topics, etc.) towards bringing METICOS main results in higher TRL levels and commercialization.
4. Dedicated business models will be provided for the exploitable outcomes of the project and a business plan for the main exploitable outcome.
5. Targeted workshops organized by METICOS in order to facilitate the exploitation activities of the project, further establishing communication channels with key industrial & targeted stakeholders.

5.1 Overview of METICOS Exploitable Results

The exploitable results as those are seen at the very beginning of the project and project activities. A better understanding and a more detailed presentation are expected for the upcoming deliverable reports relevant to the Dissemination and exploitation that are expected on project months 18 and 36.

1. **METICOS Platform**
2. **METICOS Components (as those are presented below)**
3. **Scientific Knowledge**
4. **Policy Recommendations**
5. **Results of the pilots**

Figure 17 METICOS Platform components

Besides the identification of the exploitable results, and although too early, taking into account that this deliverable report is formulated on Month 6 of the project, an initial 5 years (after the completion of the project activities) financial analysis has been developed examining both individuals as well as joint exploitation scenarios assuming that (a) the individual components of the proposed solution will find their way to the market as a stand-alone solution or coupled with other; (b) the integrated solution can be exploited as part of a joint venture, and (c) the unit sales of the components and the integrated solution will rise exponential before starting by a low initial volume. The results of this analysis are

indicative but provide a good estimation of the potential value of the project results and their associated impact in terms of new job creation. A series of initial assumptions and projections have been made, even from the proposal stage of METICOS project. However, detailed information will be presented in the upcoming period, on project Deliverable 11.2 *“Dissemination, communication and exploitation progress report”* that will be available on project month 18.

5.2 Exploitation Working Group

In order to secure the proper and on-time achievement of the above, project partners have agreed to establish an Exploitation Working Group, consisting of one representative of each consortium partner. The EWG holds re role/responsibility to proceed with the actual implementation of activities, establishment of relevant contacts, and represent METICOS project to local/national/international third parties/initiatives. The EWG will take all the decisions relevant to the implementation of Task 11.2, support the identification, exploitation, and utilization of the project exploitable outcomes, explore and identify target stakeholders and relevant groups, identify tangible financial plans, develop dedicated financial plans per identified stakeholder, and business models while organising targeted workshops that will also feed to the above-mentioned activities, exploring the possibilities of involving third parties (as consultants or verification factors) to the activities described and expected under the relevant project task.

The Exploitation Working Group will meet once per month, online, via the GoToMeeting Application. Minutes will be kept and shared with all members, while an online action plan and a corresponding online reporting document will be held to secure the progress of activities. The EWG is expected to collaborate with other Boards established inside the Consortium such as the Security Advisory Board as well as with the Advisory Board, which is expected to provide the EWG with crucial feedback/verification on the exploitation plans, the financial plans and as well as with the Business Models (per category of stakeholder).

METICOS EXPLOITATION WORKING GROUP MEMBERS		
1	ViLabs	Charalampos Chatzimallis
2	EUC	Christiana Themistocleous
3	ICCS	Gregoris Mentzas (Substitute: Babis Magoutas)
4	NetU	Project Manager
5	NTNU	Sule Yildirim Yayilgan, Erjon Zoto, Mohamed Abomhara, Sarang Shaikh
6	VUB	Franck Dumortier
7	SIMAVI	Monica Florea
8	AIT	Raimund Schatz
9	JOAFG	Georg Aumayr
10	MAGG	Katerina Margariti
11	MoCP/EDPD	Representative
12	PPA	Representative
13	ITPF	Representative
14	SBGS	Representative
15	CY-POL	Representative

Table 9 METICOS Exploitation Working Group Members

5.3 Joint and Individual Exploitation Plans

5.3.1 Joint Exploitation Plan

METICOS partners have initially agreed to jointly commercialize the METICOS Integrating Platform by creating a partnership/ joint venture. The new entity will provide business clients with the overall solution, while some partners will also act as third party big data service providers (e.g., by offering their own services through the METICOS Ecosystem) under specific terms and business framework that will be detailed and agreed upon during the project implementation as part of (a) the business planning and exploitation activities, (b) the SLAs that will govern the relationship of the marketplace administrators and the third-party providers. The role and share of each partner on the joint venture will be determined on the basis of the described foreground and IPR assets identified. On this basis, during the project, METICOS partners will explore joint exploitation alternatives in line with their individual interests and resolve potential conflicts arising from their individual exploitation plans. To finance the commercialization of the project results and for scaling up METICOS will consider the use of private and public funds from sources such as the [EU investment plan](#) and private investors.

5.3.2 Individual (per partner) Exploitation Plans

Current Individual Dissemination and Exploitation Activities
<p>European University Cyprus. Researchers, junior faculty and students will be educated through research conducted along the lines of METICOS in the form of theses, fellowships or research internships in industrial or other academic partners. EUC intends to disseminate projects outcomes through: 1) Public lectures & demonstrations: given by scientists, for providing the audience with their scientific insights and excitement with theoretical and practical demonstrations; 2) Journal and International Conferences publications: The achieved scientific results will be published in Open Access Journals, and also in leading scientific journals; 3) Participation in industrial exhibitions and related EU events.</p>
<p>ICCS Participation in the METICOS project is a great opportunity to increase technology transfer targeting enterprises and organizations interested in data analytics in various domains, including border security. Moreover, based on METICOS results, ICCS will be able to start new research lines that allow the development of follow-up research ideas and projects, the dissemination of the results in the scientific community and the use of the created knowledge to expand the researcher workforce in the form of finished Bachelor, Master, Diploma and PhD theses.</p>
<p>NET-U: The development of innovative systems for smart border control is an important part of the future growth strategy at NET-U. To this end, using the METICOS project results, NET-U aims to enrich and improve its existing go to market product portfolio, infuse its existing products with cutting-edge data and privacy protection techniques and infuse the development of its future border control products with predictive analytics and smart decision-making functionalities. NET-U will also exploit the METICOS project partnership in order to expand its collaboration and customer portfolio across Europe. NET-U aims to raise awareness about the project and generate industrial interest by informing relevant local stakeholders such as border authorities, key influencers, policymakers and researchers on the innovation, results and outputs of METICOS project. It will also collect feedback from experts beyond the project’s Consortium and explore collaboration</p>

opportunities within the project and beyond. NET-U’s dissemination will be implemented through both online and offline means. First of all, the company’s website will include information about the project and the project’s results. Moreover, online dissemination will be boosted through the use of the company’s social media accounts. Beyond online dissemination, NetU will also promote the project through presentations of the project’s objectives and results at local and European events as well as through the distribution of the project’s leaflets.

NTNU will make large use of all their online and offline media capacities, including social media posts up to various social events happening around the year. The University is also hosting many scientific conferences or other similar events on a yearly basis, and the community participating in such activities would be introduced with details from this on-going project and the main deliverables it is expected to produce and the results. NTNU is an important partner for many other companies and organizations, on a national and global level, giving more opportunity to share information on the project and other relevant details. NTNU will make proper use of the modules and tools developed from its staff within the project duration, and at the same time try and test the modules created from other partners as well, as a way to further validate and promote the project’s expected outcomes. Besides this, the Technological Transfer Office of NTNU is open to receive, evaluate and support ideas for startups. For that reason, NTNU will present the work and the scope of relevant WP to TTO and will look into opportunities for a startup together with its partners from the METICOS project.

VUB METICOS will advance VUB’s border and security portfolio by further developing and expanding our expertise in systems for border management, as well as by further refining and implementing our privacy (plus) impact assessment methodology. This project will enable VUB to acquire knowledge, capacities and experience that will give them an advantage in relation to their competition when bidding for the design and delivery of services related to impact assessments in future tenders and grants. Importantly VUB hopes to undertake innovative research in relation to developing an approach as to how to incorporate human rights as a fundamental axis into technological designs. This methodology will be exploited through journal articles and conference presentations.

SIMAVI: SIMAVI experience in the customs field has been acquired over 15 years of designing and implementing integrated complex IT solutions. The eCustoms solution developed by SIMAVI Romania is recognized as a competitive solution at European level ensuring:

- automating and increasing the efficiency of customs’ business processes
- compliance with national and European customs regulations
- adaptability and interoperability
- easy integration with existing applications
- connecting economic operators with customs authorities, in view of the electronic information exchange contained in the customs declarations and in other documents related to the circulation of goods

By developing 3 essential modules for METICOS solution: **Advance Data Mining Engine, Universal Connector with Modern BCP Risk Assessment Platform and Interfaces with customs identification systems**, SIMAVI will implement these results in its next generation products for Custom and Border Units and will add these new features to its portfolio of services. This will strengthen its competitive position in the Custom related market, open new cooperation opportunities and extend its ability to generate new research funding from external sources.

SIMAVI, as technological partner, will be involved in dissemination actions in order to support the specific activities on the cyber security and security market. Based on the security strategy set at company level, SIMAVI will increase its role of technological partner for this market sector, which will place it among the key

players in the security domain. Therefore, SIMAVI will participate in specific events (conferences, seminars, workshops) where the results to which the company contributed in the development process will be presented for a full exposure of the efforts and to identify potential needs or requirements to address in future.

AIT: In terms of individual exploitation, AIT plans to expand and strengthen its portfolio of consulting services related to technology experience and acceptance. Within the project, AIT expects to grow in particular its expertise and skills in the area of privacy-sensitive technologies, multi-cultural technology acceptance, and data-driven experience. Potential key sectors and industries for exploitation include: (i) National security, immigration, and border control. (ii) Private security and access control, (iii) Banking, (iv) Health, (v) Public transport, (vi) Tourism.

Concerning dissemination, AIT plans the following activities during project execution:

- 1) AIT will conduct a workshop with representatives of the Vienna International Airport, to demonstrate the relevance and importance of the project for border authorities.
- 2) Besides METICOS, AIT is involved in several other research projects which investigate border control related issues and solutions. For example, in the project FastPass (FP7-SEC-2012-1), optimal and harmonized Automated Border Control (ABC) implementations are evaluated. We plan to combine the learnings and outputs of both projects to demonstrate the usefulness of the projects in the contexts of road-shows and/or workshops with border control authorities.

JOAFG: The individual exploitation plan for METICOS will aim to enhance its know-how in no-gate crossing technologies and methodologies as it is a part of the mission and vision of JOAFG for international cooperation and relief actions. The dissemination plan will focus on raising project awareness at the aforementioned Conferences. The JOAFG Website will feature a subsection on the project, announcements can be posted on the website and in the internal and external newsletters for large events or milestones. Social media Platforms can post news more frequently. The Project will be associated with the JOAFG on Researchgate. Furthermore, public presentations of the project can be held at major events taking place (for example, on public holidays) in Austria. To raise further awareness for the project, JOAFG can make use of its international Network, for example via JOIN (Johanniter International).

MAGG The company strongly supports the platform to be implemented by the METICOS project, as it believes that the methods and tools to be developed through the proposed project are of broad interest towards its extending target. To this end, MAGG intends to play an active role in this process as a system integrator and a software-as-a-service solutions provider, identifying the platform to be developed as an important tool for the future Security and SaaS-based corporate strategy. MAGG will undertake to disseminate the METICOS project results at the best possible level. As a leading integrator, IT services provider, and enterprise application systems vendor in the Balkan market, the Telecommunication, Health and the public sector, MAGG intends to disseminate the project results to its wide customer base as well as to its authorized business partners' network, numbering more than 500 partners in the Balkan market. The goal of MAGG's dissemination activities will be to create awareness in the communities of stakeholders addressed by the project and attracting customers. MAGG will undertake pre-marketing activities, such as creating lists of potential customers and organizing targeted demonstrations to interested parties.

VILABS will be able to enlarge its know-how from the knowledge generated and will allow them, to expand and improve its services portfolio, offering new and/or improved services, on no-border solutions and on leveraging gender dimension into security contents. This will help them to increase their customer base and revenues and, in addition, enlarge their network of relevant stakeholders, creating larger visibility of their companies and the potential of new collaborations and expansions of their activities.

5.3.3 Intellectual Property Rights

The IPR strategy and the exploitation management are being handled in the Consortium Agreement, as well as in dedicated tasks of project WP1 Task. The IPR strategy of the project is an important part of the project exploitation plan. During the project meetings, the internal results will be reviewed with the goal of identifying important ideas and defining an individual strategy for the positioning of these ideas in the standardisation and commercialisation processes. The project results will be updated. An initial plan has already been formulated. However, information about this but will be presented in the upcoming period, on project Deliverable 11.2 “Dissemination, communication and exploitation progress report” that will be available on project month 18.

6. Monitoring and Evaluation

METICOS elaborates a specific evaluation strategy to monitor its dissemination and communication efforts. The goal of such an option is to provide concrete evidence about the effectiveness of METICOS's dissemination and exploitation efforts, as well as insights on how to amplify its reach and impact. The periodic review and update of the project Dissemination Plan will depend on the data source in the dissemination and communication reports based on the discussed set of assessments. The monitoring and evaluation tools of such responsibility are going to assess METICOS efforts in a qualitative and quantitative fashion. The procedures implemented are the following:

- **Action plan creation and communication inside the Consortium.** A specific list of activities concentrates all the projected dissemination and communication actions that partners have to undertake. This list comprises pre-defined and scheduled tasks, but it will also include partners' individual plans for dissemination and communication activities which, due to their nature, cannot be precisely pre-organised, like the participation in upcoming conferences and networking events. This database will organise the activities as a whole in order for each partner to know what they are supposed to do and when. In addition, based on this inclusive schedule, partners will receive bi-monthly updates by VILABS about their dissemination and communication tasks.
- **Dissemination and communication activities reporting by all partners.** When an opportunity for a dissemination activity emerges, partners notify WP11 leader about it. The Dissemination team documents such action accordingly and provide any necessary assistance (e.g., guidelines, tips for better communication, etc.). What is more, upon the completion of any form of their assigned dissemination activity, partners fill in the specific dissemination reporting form so that a robust book-keeping of dissemination and communication efforts is made. METICOS is using an appropriate template where all particular information on the type of the activity and a series of simple, yet necessary, details of it is included. The template is provided as Annex at the end of this document report.
- **Monitoring of participation in events.** As mentioned above, activities within the dissemination and communication framework are carefully evaluated in order to ensure the best possible dissemination of the project. Examples of such monitoring include guidelines to participating partners to inform them on how to communicate METICOS (tips for photos taken from events, METICOS's banners, etc.) and/or assistance with presentation preparation.
- **Statistics of visibility, traffic, reach and engagement rates of METICOS's website and social media platforms.** This allows partners to better understand the most appropriate timing, communication style and target audience of each message. Furthermore, such metrics are essential for planning re-adjustments.

As a result, the planning follows the Grant Agreement's information and elaborates on how the predefined outline is going to be specifically scheduled and actualised according to the afore discussed strategy. To this end, the presented tools and channels of METICOS's dissemination and communication are matched with the objectives found on the Grant Agreement of the project. Below, the table from Grant Agreement comprises the general course of dissemination and communication actions throughout METICOS lifecycle.

6.1 METICOS initial dissemination plan and KPIs

Dissemination activity or material	Main Objective	Target Audience
Development and maintenance of the project website	The project website will spread the objectives and results as widely as possible.	At least 5000 visitors will have accessed the website by the end of the project.
Production of project documentation and printing costs	The project brochure will be a key document, to be disseminated by the Consortium as a whole and by each Consortium partner, as widely as possible.	500 copies of the project brochure or digital copies will be distributed throughout the project duration.
Organisation of presentation / feedback sessions (1 per year at major forums or trade shows, relevant to the project theme)	Key stakeholders from Europe and beyond will be invited to presentation / feedback sessions, to provide the project with their inputs (visions and alternative solutions).	An attendance of 40-70 delegates is considered.
Organisation of a training session	A series of data security applications developers training to METICOS solutions will be held in cooperation with key stakeholder groups, to enable new users to experiment the solutions and to provide their feedback.	An attendance of 20-30 delegates including representatives from the METICOS end-users

Table 10 METICOS Initial dissemination plan and KPIs

6.2 METICOS initial Communication and Dissemination Objectives and KPIs

Comm. Objective	Year One	Year Two	Year Three
Create Project Identity and Branding	Create project branding and identity. Finalize Logo and colour scheme.	Revise Branding and Identity as required by project partners	Revise Branding and Identity as required by project partners.
Design Dissemination Materials	Create dissemination materials including giveaways, leaflets, brochure, poster and other materials.	Update materials according to project feedback. Create versions in other languages where possible with project partners.	Update materials according to project feedback. Create versions in other languages where possible with project partners.
Create Project Website	Take project website live including the information about consortium	Update the website with portal information and open data repository.	Update open data repository and add access

	members and project function.		to the METICOS open repository platform.
Implement effective social media strategy	Facebook/Twitter/LinkedIn/Instagram: 1000 followers total	YouTube – 1 Videos live w. 5000 hits Facebook/Twitter/LinkedIn/Instagram: 3000 followers total	YouTube – 2 Videos live w. 10000 hits Facebook/Twitter/LinkedIn/Instagram: 5000 followers total
Networking events and workshops (physical and/or online)	Attend and/or host up to 3 relevant networking events or workshops addressing the target communities, stakeholders and end-users	Attend and/or host up to 5 relevant networking events or workshops addressing the target communities, stakeholders and users.	Attend and/or host up to 5 relevant networking events or workshops addressing the target communities, stakeholders and users.
Generate positive media coverage & releasing project publications	2 newsletters 1-3 project publications (articles and/or papers and/or presentation) At least 10 blog entries	2 newsletters 2-4 project publications At least 20 blog entries	3 newsletters 2-4 project publications more than 20 blog entries
Cluster with Relevant Projects & initiatives	Cluster with 1 relevant project or global initiative, including other SEC projects	Cluster with 2 relevant projects or global initiatives	Cluster with 5 relevant projects or global initiatives

Table 11 6.2 METICOS initial Communication and Dissemination Objectives and KPIs

6.3 METICOS Dissemination and Communication Summary Chart

Communication & Dissemination Supports & Channels	KPIs	Main Target Stakeholders			
		Border Sector	Control	End-Users	Facilitators
Project Documentation					
Leaflet (digital)	1 initial version + updates if needed	X		X	X
Poster (digital)	1 initial version + updates if needed	O		X	O
Reference PPT presentation	1 initial version + updates if needed	X		X	X
Project Publications					

Project newsletter	6 (semestrial issue)	X	X	O
BES Cluster Joint Newsletter	2	X	X	X
Articles and proceedings	3 publications per year (in average)	O	X	O
Project deliverables	See list of deliverables	X	X	X
Open access repository	1 deposit per year	X	O	O
Project video / slideshow	1 initial version + update	X	X	X
Online Presence				
Project website	1 website, monthly updated	X	X	X
Related websites	10+	Depending on specific Website		
LinkedIn	At least 1 monthly update	X	X	X
Twitter/Facebook	At least 1 weekly update	X	X	X
YouTube	3 Videos by the end of the project	X	X	X
Events				
Presentation & feedback sessions	3	X	O	O
Training sessions	3	O	X	O
BES CLUSTER Workshop	3	X	X	X
External events	15+	Depending on specific event		
Caption:				
X	Main target			
O	Secondary target			

Table 12 Dissemination and Communication Summary Chart

7. Conclusions

This document provides an overview of the project dissemination, communication and engagement strategy, highlighting its key elements:

- The reason and objectives of communication and dissemination
- The project target groups
- The key communication messages
- The various dissemination channels and tools that will be used
- The planning and evaluation of dissemination activities.
- The sustainability and exploitation initial approach

The dissemination plan presented in this deliverable covers the initial strategy that was to be followed by the project and presents the progress achieved until M6. Partners will use (are using the strategy provided via) this document as the initial strategy which will constantly be under evaluation. Any adjustments related to the dissemination plan together with progress in dissemination activities will be reported in the two periodic reports that are to be submitted to the European Commission (M18) and (M36). In addition, updates on the dissemination activities will be included in the relevant upcoming deliverables, D.11.2. “Dissemination, communication and exploitation progress report” and D11.3. “Dissemination, communication and exploitation final progress report”.

8. Appendices

Appendix 1: METICOS Guide on Dissemination and Communication

This informal guide acts as a reminder checklist for partners to contribute to the project's dissemination and communication plan during the whole project duration. It will be cross-checked by the coordinator and the dissemination leader during every partner's meeting where a relevant presentation of dissemination activities will take place. The METICOS dissemination and communication guide is the following:

1. Inform VILABS (briefly via email) about any dissemination or communication activity related to METICOS, i.e., Presentation, Publication, Participation in events. etc.
2. Inform VILABS about relevant events, where METICOS partners could participate (e.g. Conferences, Seminars etc.), so that the events database can be updated respectively. If necessary, arrangements could be made so that METICOS will be represented.
3. Collect photos, videos, from all METICOS activities (full documentation): meetings, workshops, seminars, press conferences, etc. Send them to VILABS to be used in publicity material (e.g. project newsletters, videos, etc.). Take care that there are no third party intellectual property rights.
4. Use in all of your communications (deliverables, presentations, newsletters, etc.) the METICOS logo, the EU flag and the statement This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 883075
5. To avoid conflicts, coordinate with other partners and inform VILABS on intention to publish from METICOS. Always mention the financing body (EU / Horizon 2020).
6. Invite local policymakers in appropriate projects stages and inform them of the project's progress. Record events (videos - photos). Send them to VILABS.
7. Forward Press releases, Newsletters and other materials to your contacts that might be interested to METICOS's objectives and thematic interests.
8. Feel free to provide material for regularly updating the METICOS website.
9. Follow METICOS's social media pages (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Research Gate), as a follower. Monitor the announcements and posts, "like" them, comment on them. Make your own posts on METICOS's social media accounts. Connect with people. Initiate the dialogue or take part in it.

Appendix 2 – Dissemination of Activities reporting template

In order to keep track of the project/partners dissemination activities, a reporting procedure has been developed to support all partners as well as the partner leading the communication and dissemination activities.

A dedicated folder has been generated within the METICOS repository, with a series of sub-folders dedicated to the different kinds of communication and dissemination activities, so that partners can report activities according to their type. Moreover and in order to secure that all the needed information is going to be shared accordingly a “dissemination activities reporting template” has been formulated and shared with the Consortium.

One can find below an image depicting the way the folders have been structured as well as the very reporting template shared with partners.

Folder reporting structure:

Name	Modified	Modified By
1 Press Release	December 22, 2020	chatzimallis
10 Training	December 22, 2020	chatzimallis
11 Exhibition	December 22, 2020	chatzimallis
15 Flyer	December 22, 2020	chatzimallis
16 Social Media	December 22, 2020	chatzimallis
17 Website	December 22, 2020	chatzimallis
18 Other	December 22, 2020	chatzimallis
19 Newsletters	December 22, 2020	chatzimallis
2 Popularized Publication	December 22, 2020	chatzimallis
3 Communication Campaign	December 22, 2020	chatzimallis
5 Organization of a Conference	December 22, 2020	chatzimallis
6 Participation to a Conference	December 22, 2020	chatzimallis
7 Organization of a Workshop	December 22, 2020	chatzimallis
8 Participation to a Workshop	December 22, 2020	chatzimallis
9 Participation to an Event other	December 22, 2020	chatzimallis
Dissemination activities reporting_template...	December 22, 2020	chatzimallis

Figure 18 METICOS Folder reporting structure

Reporting template provided to all partners

Dissemination activities reporting

Guidelines: Before reporting any information, please, make sure to make a copy of this document and rename it with the name of the activity and your institution’s acronym. Secure your file in the dedicated folder on Teams:

For further details or information, send an email to chatzimalis@vilabs.eu

Choose the type of the Dissemination and Communication activity you are reporting.

- Press Release
- Non-Scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularized publication)
- Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV, etc.)
- Video/Film
- Organization of a Conference
- Participation in a Conference
- Organization of a Workshop
- Participation in a Workshop
- Participation in an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop
- Organization of an Awareness Raising Event
- Training
- Exhibition
- Brokerage Event
- Pitch Event
- Trade Fair
- Participation in other activities organized jointly with other (H2020) projects
- Flyer
- Social Media
- Website
- Other

Template for reporting the participation of METICOS in activities

General Information	
XXXXXXXXXX	
Name of event	
Date	
Location	
Event organizer	
Event website	
Description of the event (objectives, target audience etc.)	
Results	
Meticos Partners attending the event	
Type of participation (brief descriptions of activities)	
Estimated number of participants reached**	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific community (higher education, research): • Industry:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil Society: • General public: • Policy Makers: • Media: • Investors: • Customers: • Other:
Pictures	Add one or two here! For the rest please make a folder with the name of the event.
Remarks/Recommendations	
Website	
Short description to be added under 'news' in the project's website	

